

Focus Group and Survey Report on the Role of Libraries During Crises

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Abstract:	This report presents key findings from a survey and focus group on the role of university libraries during crises. It highlights a gap between the widespread trust in libraries and their actual use, identifies common barriers to engagement, and outlines opportunities to enhance their crisis response capacity through improved visibility, support services, and public engagement.
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List of Abbreviations

The following table presents the acronyms used in the deliverable in alphabetical order.

Abbreviations	Description
D2	Deliverable 2
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
WP2A2	Work Package 2, Activity 2
WP3A2	Work Package 3, Activity 2
SKS	SKS Knowledge Services

Executive Summary

This Deliverable 2 (D2) of the CAELUM project (Open Science Supporting Vulnerable Communities: Empowering University Libraries in Crisis Response, project number 2024-1-EE01-KA220-HED-000243324) presents findings from an online survey and a focus group conducted by SKS Knowledge Services under Work Package 2, Activity 2 (WP2A2). The objective was to explore the role of academic libraries in supporting students, staff, and researchers during various crises, and to identify gaps, needs, and future opportunities for institutional response and resilience building.

The research employed a mixed-methods approach. A total of 45 valid responses were collected through an anonymous online survey, supplemented by a 90-minute focus group discussion involving eight academic stakeholders. Participants reflected on both personal and institutional experiences with crises, including pandemics, geopolitical conflict, climate disruptions, and the growing challenge of information overload. The analysis yielded five thematic areas: perceptions of libraries during crises; expectations and needs of academic communities; barriers to access and engagement; the library's role in fostering public resilience; and the emergent issue of information overload as a distinct crisis.

Key findings indicate that while libraries are widely perceived as trusted, safe, and adaptable institutions, this symbolic trust does not always translate into practical engagement during crises. Despite 84% of respondents expressing comfort in turning to libraries for help, fewer than half reported actually doing so during a crisis. This highlights a trust–usage gap. Users respect and value libraries conceptually but often turn to more immediate or familiar sources such as government websites, social media, or personal networks when under pressure. Barriers such as limited visibility, constrained communication, inadequate resources, and unclear institutional positioning hinder libraries' ability to fully realize their potential as effective frontline support institutions during crises. This contributes to a persistent gap between symbolic trust and actual engagement, even when services are available.

At the same time, the research identifies significant opportunities: high interest in credibility-focused workshops, growing demand for emotional and mental health support, and the capacity of libraries to act as curators of reliable information amidst digital saturation.

The report concludes that academic libraries have a unique and expanding role in crisis response, not only as access points to knowledge, but as civic actors that foster trust, resilience, and inclusion. A series of targeted recommendations are proposed to strengthen libraries' crisis readiness, including enhanced communication strategies, staff capacity building, cross-sector collaboration, and proactive engagement with users experiencing digital overwhelm.

The results of this activity will directly inform the design of WP3A2, where SKS will lead a case study on information overload in academic environments. More broadly, the deliverable contributes to the evidence base for co-developing inclusive, sustainable, and crisis-responsive library services across Europe.

1. Introduction

1.1. Background

This document constitutes Deliverable 2 (D2) of the CAELUM project (*Open Science Supporting Vulnerable Communities: Empowering University Libraries in Crisis Response*, project number 2024-1-EE01-KA220-HED-000243324), funded under the Erasmus+ programme. The report presents the results of online survey and focus group activities conducted under Work Package 2, Activity 2 (WP2A2).

CAELUM investigates how university libraries can strengthen their role in times of crisis through inclusive services, civic engagement, and open science-based practices. It addresses growing demands placed on academic libraries to act not only as knowledge providers but also as responsive and supportive institutions for vulnerable communities during periods of disruption.

Within this framework, WP2A2 was designed to generate empirical insights from multiple stakeholder perspectives and to support the development of evidence-based models for crisis-responsive academic libraries.

The main aim of WP2A2 is to gather qualitative and quantitative insights from academic stakeholders to better understand the perceived and actual roles of libraries in times of crisis, identify gaps and good practices, and inform the co-creation of future interventions in WP3.

The specific objectives of WP2A2 are:

1. To map crisis experiences from the perspectives of library users and staff across diverse university contexts.
2. To identify expectations and perceived needs regarding academic library support during and after crisis situations.
3. To explore barriers and structural limitations faced by university libraries when addressing crises.
4. To explore how university libraries can foster civic engagement and contribute to community resilience through their crisis-related functions.

In CAELUM, crises are understood in a broad and evolving sense, encompassing both acute and prolonged disruptions that affect individuals, institutions, and communities. These include large-scale health emergencies such as the COVID-19 pandemic, geopolitical conflicts and war-related displacement (for example, the war in Ukraine), climate-related disasters, economic

insecurity, and sociotechnical challenges like digital disinformation and information overload. These types of crises often disproportionately affect vulnerable groups, including people with disabilities who may face additional barriers in accessing information, support services, and safe environments. These crises not only strain public systems and institutions but also disrupt everyday academic life, mental health, social cohesion, and access to trustworthy information.

Within this context, university libraries are conceptualized as more than custodians of knowledge or academic service providers. They are positioned as responsive civic actors with the potential to contribute to community resilience, mental and emotional support, inclusive access to information, and open, participatory research. Libraries can serve as physical and symbolic safe spaces, offering reliable information, digital access, and social care, especially for vulnerable or marginalized populations. They can also act as mediators between academia and society by supporting science communication, digital literacy, and public engagement with socially relevant knowledge. CAELUM thus envisions libraries as central institutions in both immediate crisis response and long-term community recovery.

1.2. Scope

This D2 report presents the WP2A2 results from **SKS Knowledge Services**, a CAELUM project partner. SKS coordinated anonymised data collection, conducted an online survey (n=45), and facilitated a focus group discussion involving eight participants representing a diverse mix of academic librarians, students, and researchers. The data collected provides insights into how university libraries are perceived in crisis contexts, the challenges they face, and the expectations of their user communities.

While the core aim of WP2A2 was to explore general crisis response roles and perceptions, SKS also included a limited number of exploratory questions related to information overload. This addition was intended to support and enrich the upcoming phase of the project which is Work Package 3, Activity 2 (WP3A2). For this upcoming activity, each CAELUM partner will implement a national case study to test and refine the CAELUM approach in real-world academic environments. These case studies will focus on different types of crises or community needs based on local contexts. For SKS, the central theme will be information overload, examining how the overwhelming volume, speed, and fragmentation of information affect students, researchers, and academic staff. This focus responds to growing concerns around digital fatigue, and the capacity to engage meaningfully with open science. The findings from WP2A2 will directly inform the design and framing of this case study.

1.3. Research questions

This report addresses the following research questions defined by the CAELUM consortium:

- **RQ1:** What has been the libraries' role during crises?
- **RQ2:** What are the expectations and perceived needs of students, academic staff, and library professionals regarding library support in crisis situations?
- **RQ3:** What barriers and gaps have university libraries faced in responding to crises?
- **RQ4:** How can university libraries contribute to public engagement and community resilience during and after crises?

In addition, SKS formulated a partner-specific research question to guide its future work in WP3A2 and to leverage this WP2A2 activity as an opportunity for early insights:

- **SKS-RQ:** What preliminary insights can be drawn about the experience and perception of information overload among academic stakeholders, and how might these inform future library-based interventions?

1.4. Structure

The report is structured as follows:

- **Section 2** outlines the methodology, including participant profiles and data collection instruments.
- **Section 3** presents the key results from both the survey and focus group, organized by emergent themes.
- **Section 4** provides a discussion of challenges and opportunities for crisis responsive libraries.
- **Section 5** summarizes the conclusions based on the survey and focus group findings.

2. Methodology

This section outlines the methodological approach used to investigate how university libraries can better support vulnerable communities during times of crisis. A mixed-methods strategy was employed, combining an online survey and a focus group discussion. The dual approach enabled both breadth and depth: the survey provided quantitative trends and broad sentiment across a diverse set of participants, while the focus group offered qualitative insight into lived experiences, expectations, and emotional nuances. Together, these methods allowed for a deeper understanding of user perceptions and the institutional gaps libraries may address in times of instability.

2.1. Data collection

2.1.1. Online Survey

An anonymous online survey was conducted by SKS in May 2025, as part of the broader CAELUM initiative. The questionnaire was developed by CAELUM consortium and designed to collect insights from both academic library users and professionals. The survey comprised 21 items, combining both closed- and open-ended questions, and was organized into five thematic blocks: *library roles during crises*, *expectations and needs*, *barriers and support gaps*, *public engagement and community support*. In addition, SKS added exploratory items related to *information overload*, supporting the forthcoming WP3 case study. While the information overload section was optional, all respondents chose to complete it. The instrument was internally piloted to ensure clarity, coherence, and accessibility across academic roles.

The survey was disseminated through convenience sampling, using institutional mailing lists and academic networks. A total of 45 valid responses were received. While not statistically representative, the sample offered a diverse range of professional insights. Respondents were primarily academic staff (36%) and library professionals (38%), with others identifying as students or researchers. Over half (53%) of the participants were aged between 46–60, and 22% were over 60, suggesting responses came from individuals with substantial institutional and life experience.

2.1.2. Focus Group Discussion

To enrich the quantitative data and explore more nuanced perspectives, a focus group was conducted by SKS at the end of May 2025. The group consisted of eight participants, purposively selected to ensure diversity in lived experience and professional background.

Participants included academic librarians, students, and researchers from higher education institutions; all of whom brought valuable insight from direct or institutional experiences with crisis situations in academic environments.

The session lasted approximately 90 minutes and was conducted online, enabling broader participation and geographic inclusion. It followed a semi-structured discussion guide jointly developed by the CAELUM consortium. The conversation explored key themes such as past experiences with crisis events, the perceived and desired role of academic libraries during such times, institutional challenges, and expectations for the future. The discussion also included a dedicated segment on information overload, probing whether participants had personally experienced such crises, how they defined them, and what role they believed libraries could play in mitigating the effects.

The session was recorded, transcribed, anonymised, and participants provided informed consent in line with ethical research protocols and data protection standards. The focus group added significant qualitative depth to the survey results, allowing for more contextualized interpretation and stakeholder-informed reflection.

2.2. Data collection

2.2.1. Descriptive statistics and comparison analysis

The survey's quantitative data were processed using Excel and Python-based tabulations. Descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentages were calculated to summarize overall trends. For certain closed-ended questions, comparison analyses were conducted using cross-tabulations to explore patterns between respondents' expectations, behaviors, and perceptions (e.g., comparing what users expect from libraries with what they personally consider most important during crises). These relational insights helped identify gaps, contradictions, or synergies that might not appear in isolated responses. While inferential statistical testing was not appropriate due to the sample size, these relational comparisons offered valuable directional insights. Open-ended survey responses were summarized thematically to supplement and contextualize the statistical findings, often highlighting emotional or experiential nuances not captured in multiple-choice items.

2.2.2. Inductive thematic analysis

An inductive thematic analysis was carried out to explore patterns and insights from the focus group discussion, drawing on the principles outlined by Braun and Clarke (2006). Rather than applying a pre-existing coding framework, themes were allowed to emerge naturally from the data, ensuring that the analysis remained grounded in participants' own language, experiences,

and perspectives. The process began with repeated close reading of the transcript to gain familiarity with the content. Key ideas, recurring phrases, and notable tensions or agreements were noted manually. Instead of using formal qualitative data software, themes were developed through handwritten and visual summaries that grouped related responses together. As researchers, we adopted an interpretive role by organizing and making sense of the data while maintaining reflexivity and striving to center participants' voices rather than impose our own assumptions. This approach supported the development of themes that authentically reflect the lived realities and perceptions of academic stakeholders regarding the role of libraries during crises.

3. Findings and discussion

This section integrates both survey and focus group findings under thematic headings, each responding to one of the five guiding research questions from the CAELUM project and the SKS-specific question. Quantitative results and qualitative reflections are combined to provide a cohesive interpretation of the data.

3.1. The role of libraries during crises

Libraries have long been perceived as stable, accessible institutions that offer continuity during times of disruption. This perception was reaffirmed in both the focus group discussion and the survey data, where libraries emerged as institutions deeply associated with trust. However, while symbolic trust remains high, actual engagement during crises appears more complex. Survey responses indicate that belief in libraries' potential does not consistently translate into use when individuals face real-time emergencies. The following subsections explore the evolving role of libraries during crises by considering perceptions, experiences, and behavioral patterns emerging from both the qualitative and quantitative data.

3.1.1. Types and perceptions of crises

The focus group opened with reflections on the crisis types that have affected university environments in recent years. These same crisis categories were reflected in the survey results, where participants identified the most impactful or commonly experienced disruptions. These included:

- **The COVID-19 pandemic**, which was selected by thirty-three percent (33%) of survey respondents as the most significant crisis.

- **Political and geopolitical disruption**, including the war in Ukraine, cited by sixteen percent (16%) of participants.
- **Climate-related disasters**, such as floods or heatwaves that disrupted academic operations.
- **Disinformation and declining public trust**, particularly in relation to fake news.
- **Internal institutional challenges**, particularly within libraries themselves, such as widening disparities in user engagement between on-site and digital users.
- **Personal and psychological crises**, especially among students studying abroad, who may experience isolation, logistical difficulties, or uncertainty about support systems.

These types of crises reflect not only systemic and global-scale challenges but also local and personal disruptions that influence how academic communities engage with support institutions like libraries.

In the focus group, participants disagreed on how to interpret the nature of these crises. Some emphasized historical continuity, suggesting that crises are a recurring feature of human experience. They referenced the first half of the twentieth century particularly World War II as a time of even greater disruption. From this viewpoint, the issues faced today are not necessarily more severe but are more widely discussed and visible due to technological and societal change. They cautioned against overemphasizing crisis narratives, which they felt could distract from practical action.

This group pointed to the COVID-19 pandemic as an example of effective and calm response by libraries. They noted that libraries transitioned quickly to digital services, expanded remote access, and supported users without delay or excessive debate. Although they acknowledged the burden of large-scale challenges such as information overload, they argued that libraries cannot directly solve such structural issues because *"they cannot tell researchers to not publish,"* as one participant put it.

Others in the group disagreed that today's crises are qualitatively different due to their overlapping and interconnected nature. This view emphasized the simultaneous presence of climate change, global supply chain instability, wars, and social unrest, all influencing one another. These participants also referenced reports by international organizations such as the United Nations and the World Economic Forum, which point to escalating global risks. They warned that individuals in relatively stable countries may experience a *"normalcy bias"* that prevents them from recognizing the severity and uniqueness of the current moment.

Despite these differences, most participants agreed that libraries must remain aware of both short-term and long-term risks. They emphasized the need for preparedness through both

traditional tools such as information access and new, adaptive strategies suited to an evolving crisis landscape.

3.1.2. Trust, Support, and the Scope of Library Engagement

Libraries are among the most trusted public institutions, and this was confirmed by both the focus group and the survey. In the survey, 84.4% of respondents stated they would feel comfortable turning to a library for help in a crisis, and 55.6% strongly agreed that libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during emergencies. Focus group participants reinforced this view, describing libraries as “neutral,” “non-political,” and “safe” spaces in moments of uncertainty.

Despite this widespread trust, survey results suggest a usage–trust gap. Only 44.4% of respondents reported having received any support from a library during a crisis, while 46.7% said they had not. This suggests a split perception of the library’s presence and role during difficult times. The remaining 8.9% were unsure, which may reflect either indirect or unrecognized support. This does not imply that support was absent, but rather reflects differing patterns of engagement, awareness, or individual needs. Libraries may offer support that some users do not access, either because their needs differ or because they are unaware of the available services. In this context, trust alone appears insufficient to drive usage during emergencies. Among those who indicated having received support from a library during a crisis, the qualitative responses emphasize a few recurring themes. Respondents most frequently mentioned access to digital resources, help in locating information, and guidance from librarians. Several noted receiving health-related updates during COVID-19, while others appreciated practical or emotional support, especially in navigating academic challenges.

Focus group participants provided multiple examples of support in action. During the COVID-19 pandemic, libraries were widely credited with adapting quickly. Measures included extending loan periods, expanding digital access to learning materials, setting up remote consultations, and guiding users through institutional changes. In some cases, librarians offered moral and even material support such as clothing or financial assistance particularly during local emergencies or for students facing difficult personal circumstances.

Beyond logistical support, several libraries introduced services that explicitly addressed emotional well-being. Focus group participants described initiatives such as bibliotherapy sessions, which allowed students to reflect on their challenges through guided reading, and the creation of quiet rooms to offer safe, peaceful environments, especially for vulnerable groups like refugees or students experiencing mental health challenges. These examples show that libraries were not only service providers but also spaces of care and continuity during times of disruption.

Despite these efforts, there is still a need to strengthen awareness and visibility of such services. Strengthening communication and access remains a key challenge in converting institutional readiness into user experience.

3.1.3. Belief vs behaviour: where do people actually go for crisis information?

Although libraries are widely trusted, this trust does not always result in active engagement. To better understand this dynamic, survey results on actual information-seeking behavior during crises were compared with their level of agreement with the statement that “libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises”. This analysis showed that users may believe in the library’s importance yet still turn elsewhere when immediate information is needed.

Even among those who strongly agreed with the library’s potential role, only about 12% reported using library channels during a crisis. In contrast, government websites and academic journals were cited more frequently. Surprisingly, “friends and family” appeared consistently as an information source across all trust levels reinforcing the strong role of interpersonal networks in crisis navigation.

Perhaps most intriguing is that approximately 19% of respondents who “strongly disagreed” with the library’s crisis role still reported using library channels. This seems contradictory but likely reflects one of several things: routine or default usage of academic library platforms (e.g., databases or portals); negative perceptions despite continued use; or inconsistency in how respondents interpreted the survey. In other words, use does not equal belief indicating strategic implications.

Figure 1: Sources of crisis information by trust in libraries.

Own source.

This comparison highlights a critical gap: symbolic trust does not automatically translate to their use in real-time crises. Even respondents who believe libraries are important often turn to faster, more familiar tools like news media, social platforms, or institutional messaging when under pressure. On the flip side, some who use library tools may not even view them as crisis-relevant. Trust is the foundation; but in this data, we learn that trust without visibility is passive and may result in libraries being respected yet overlooked when urgency strikes. Libraries must work to convert belief into behavior.

3.2. Expectations and perceived needs in a crisis

This section addresses the expectations and perceived needs of students, academic staff, and library professionals concerning the role of libraries during crises. Findings from both the survey and focus group discussions reveal that users look to libraries not only for access to information, but also for infrastructure, emotional support, and more proactive engagement.

As shown in the below figure, academic library users place the highest importance on access to reliable information and infrastructure during times of crisis. Access to credible, curated information was rated as “very important” by 74% of respondents. This was followed by reliable internet access (65%) and access to digital and full-text resources (63%). These responses

highlight that information access remains a core expectation in crisis contexts, confirming the central role libraries play in ensuring academic continuity.

Figure 2: Perceived importance of library services during a crisis.

Own Source.

When asked what kinds of support they would expect from libraries specifically, respondents selected very similar priorities. Access to curated information was the most common expectation (76.7%), followed by internet access (58.1%) and guidance from librarians (51.2%). This alignment suggests that user expectations generally correspond well with perceived needs during crises, particularly regarding the informational and infrastructural functions of libraries.

However, there were also some notable differences. While over 60% of respondents considered mental health support personally important in a crisis, only 32.6% expected libraries to offer it. Similarly, although community connection was a personal priority for many, only a minority saw it as a role for libraries. These gaps suggest that while users value emotional and social

support during crises, they may not yet associate libraries with fulfilling those roles. Rather than reflecting dissatisfaction, this may indicate limited awareness of the broader support libraries can offer. Bridging this gap will require both strategic planning and cultural shifts, particularly in recognizing emotional safety and psychological resilience as legitimate components of academic success.

The open-ended responses provide additional insights. Respondents described a supportive library as one that offers both material and emotional support. Key themes included empathetic staff, a welcoming physical environment, and resources that respond to the situation at hand. Words like “*staff*” (15 mentions), “*resources*” (16), and “*space*” (12) appeared frequently. Respondents also expressed a need for flexible spaces that offer calm and opportunities for interaction. One described the ideal library as a place where one could “*communicate, relax, get away or simply hang out or study,*” supported by “*kind, polite, and knowledgeable staff.*” These insights stress the need for libraries to foster not only access, but emotional safety and community care.

Focus group participants articulated a similarly nuanced view. Expectations extended beyond basic access to include curation, critical evaluation, and guidance through overwhelming information flows. Several participants noted that libraries should serve as “*filters, not just archives,*” guiding users through credible and relevant content rather than acting as passive repositories.

The group also stressed the need for proactivity. Libraries should not wait for users to seek help but should actively reach out during crises. This includes sending targeted information, organizing training on evaluating sources, and offering emotional support mechanisms such as bibliotherapy and safe spaces.

Another strong expectation centered on collaboration: participants emphasized the need for stronger ties between libraries and other institutional units, especially student support offices. They envisioned libraries as hubs in a wider ecosystem of crisis support.

Ultimately, these findings point out that while informational and infrastructural roles remain central, there is growing recognition of libraries’ potential to contribute to well-being, community cohesion, and critical thinking. To fully meet these evolving expectations, libraries may need to invest in cross-sector collaboration, rethink their public-facing strategies, and make their broader value more visible to the communities they serve.

3.3. Barriers and gaps in crisis response

Despite the acknowledged importance of academic libraries in crisis contexts, both the survey and the focus group identified several barriers that may hinder libraries from fully realizing

their potential support role. These limitations are both external (institutional and societal) and internal (capacity and perception-related).

Survey respondents identified a range of factors that could discourage the use of library services during crises. The most commonly selected barrier was a lack of awareness about what libraries can offer, cited by 44.2% of participants. This was followed by the perception that libraries are not the most useful place to go during a crisis (37.2%), and limited opening hours or lack of remote services (30.2%). A lack of emotional safety or comfort in library spaces was also noted by over one-fifth (20.9%) of respondents.

Additionally, in open-ended responses, several themes emerged that deepened the understanding of these barriers. Respondents pointed to the lack of visibility of libraries in institutional crisis communications and decision-making processes, as well as uncertainty about what services would even be available during a crisis. Some mentioned difficulties navigating library platforms or feeling that libraries were "*not equipped for crisis response beyond regular services.*" Others indicated that libraries might be perceived as formal or intimidating spaces, especially for marginalized students or those under stress.

These findings illustrate that the gap is not merely about service provision, but about perception, communication, and relevance. Even if services exist, they may go unused if not effectively marketed or designed in ways that resonate with user needs during times of distress.

Focus Group participants identified several potential barriers that may prevent libraries from effectively supporting people during crises. These include:

- **Insufficient funding and resources**, which limit libraries' ability to expand services or innovate in response to evolving needs.
- **Lack of specialized competencies among library staff**, particularly in areas such as mental health support, crisis communication, or misinformation management.
- **Challenges in promoting and communicating the evolving roles and services of libraries**, especially in crisis contexts where users may not immediately consider the library a source of help.
- **The need for libraries to better position themselves as influential voices**, with several participants emphasizing that libraries should adopt more active roles in digital and social media environments. One suggestion was that libraries could function more like "*influencers,*" effectively reaching users where they already are online and building visibility around their crisis-related services.

These insights suggest that while libraries are trusted and capable institutions, they face internal and external barriers that may limit their visibility and perceived relevance during times of crisis.

3.4. Libraries and public engagement for resilience

Beyond their academic function, university libraries have the potential to act as active contributors to broader community resilience during crises. This section explores how both survey respondents and focus group participants envision libraries' public role in fostering civic engagement, information empowerment, and collective recovery in turbulent times.

As discussed earlier, a strong majority of respondents (over 80%) believe that libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises. Despite this widespread belief in libraries' potential, actual participation in community-focused activities remains limited. Nearly half of respondents (48.9%) have never taken part in any such event at their university library, while only one-third (33.3%) have. This gap between belief and engagement suggests that while the library's symbolic and theoretical role is appreciated, its practical visibility as a community hub may still be underdeveloped.

The few respondents who did participate in library-hosted activities mentioned forums, conferences, and guided sessions that encouraged students to explore available services. One noted how librarians *"invited students to engage with the library for different needs,"* while another reflected on more logistical roles like *"arranging study tables and supporting book organization."* These responses suggest that where library staff are visible, proactive, and engaging, users are more likely to connect.

When asked more broadly what kinds of services libraries could offer in difficult times, respondents shared ideas that were both pragmatic and visionary. Popular suggestions included the rapid dissemination of factual information, provision of basic emergency items like blankets or power banks, hosting training sessions or talks, and serving as coordinating hubs between people, institutions, and aid networks. Respondents used terms such as *access, support, resources, and information,* revealing a deep need for libraries to function not just as academic spaces, but as active civic infrastructures. One respondent summed this up powerfully: *libraries should provide "protection, know-how, and communication."*

Focus Group participants emphasized the potential for libraries to play a central role in building stronger, more resilient communities by facilitating community-driven initiatives, such as citizen science projects. The importance of libraries acting as moderators and coordinators for transdisciplinary research and community-based projects was highlighted. Participants suggested that libraries could help bridge the gap between academic and local communities, fostering mutual understanding and collaboration.

Together, the findings indicate that university libraries are seen not only as credible sources of knowledge but also as potential agents of societal resilience. Realizing this vision, however, requires more than infrastructure; it demands outreach, visibility, and a renewed commitment to public engagement.

3.5. Information overload as a crisis in itself

As academic life becomes increasingly saturated with digital content, information overload has emerged not only as a side effect of the crisis but also as a distinct crisis in itself. The survey and focus group both illuminated the cognitive and emotional toll that excessive, fragmented, and often conflicting information places on university stakeholders.

A significant number of respondents in this survey expressed their growing concern around information overload. Over two-thirds (67.4%) reported experiencing information overload in their academic or professional activities, with another 7% unsure. The primary sources contributing to this overload include social media, particularly platforms like *Facebook*, *X (formerly Twitter)*, *LinkedIn*, and messaging apps like *Telegram* and *WhatsApp*. News websites and constant media coverage also ranked highly, signaling the cross-channel saturation of content.

Looking into the impacts, respondents cited challenges like difficulty identifying relevant or high-quality content (25.4%), confusion from conflicting information (20.5%), and a general feeling of being overwhelmed (18%). These reactions reflect a broader cognitive strain that diminishes focus, productivity, and decision-making capacity. Notably, only a few mentioned collaborative shortcomings, emphasizing that the core issue lies in the information environment, not necessarily interpersonal cooperation.

To navigate this complex landscape, participants employed coping strategies such as focusing on a few trusted sources (20%), attending workshops, and consulting librarians or peers. These responses reinforce the critical value of guidance and curation, and suggest that learners are actively seeking expert filters, not more data.

While 45.5% of respondents reported feeling "confident" in their ability to evaluate information, only a quarter (25%) described themselves as "very confident." The below chart clearly reveals a confidence divide in information-seeking behavior. Those who are "very confident" in their ability to judge credibility tend to rely more on academic journals (22.9%), government websites (16.7%), and library channels (14.6%). These are formal, structured, and generally reliable sources, showing that higher confidence aligns with more critical and selective information consumption.

Figure 3: Information sources during crises by credibility confidence level.

Own Source.

In contrast, individuals with low or no confidence are most likely to depend on friends or family (33.3%) even though these sources lack verification mechanisms while emotionally trusted. They are also largely absent from the use of institutional sources like libraries or government websites.

This dynamic reveals a worrying paradox: those most at risk of misinformation are least likely to consult verified sources. It reinforces the need for libraries and institutions to bridge this gap through outreach, training, and community partnerships. Instead of expecting low-confidence users to find their way to libraries, libraries should go to where these users already are, and offer approachable tools and language for navigating credible information.

Looking at the underlying sources of overload more closely, traditional and hybrid peer-reviewed publications, preprint servers, and institutional repositories were cited as moderate to considerable contributors to stress. Despite their scholarly nature, these channels still add to the noise, particularly when quality control, access limitations, or sheer volume hinder discernment.

Open-ended suggestions emphasized the importance of curation. One respondent sharply noted, *"A library is not a dump where any sort of information should have a place... Their role is not to support information dumps, but to serve valuable knowledge."* Others echoed the need for triage support, training, and digital literacy workshops. There is a strong desire for libraries to reclaim their role as curators, not just repositories.

A high majority (86.2%) of respondents who reported experiencing information overload said they would find library-led workshops or resources on evaluating credibility and spotting disinformation useful. Even among those who were unsure about experiencing overload, two-thirds (66.7%) expressed interest in such initiatives. Notably, even the sole respondent who had not experienced overload still responded positively, further reinforcing the perceived utility of these offerings.

Figure 4: Workshop usefulness by information overload experience.

Own Source.

This strong alignment between overload experience and workshop interest suggests that libraries have a clear mandate to step into the role of educator and filter, especially during crises. Rather than passive spaces, libraries can actively help users navigate the chaos of excessive information, misinformation, and digital noise. These results validate the importance of offering practical, timely, and credibility-focused programming as both a support strategy and a visibility booster. There's demand for intervention, and libraries are already perceived as a viable provider of those solutions. The respondents' perspectives make it clear: in a world drowning in data, the library's value lies not in volume, but in judgment.

Focus group participants echoed these concerns. Several participants emphasized the need for libraries to serve as filters, not just repositories. One participant noted that the library's true

value lies not in providing "more information" but in helping users curate and contextualize what matters. Others highlighted that during the COVID-19 pandemic, curated information packages created by libraries helped them focus on credible, relevant knowledge amidst the noise.

Some cautioned, however, that libraries alone cannot solve systemic information chaos. For example, the sheer volume of academic publishing, especially during crises, can itself be overwhelming. As one participant put it, "*Libraries cannot tell researchers to stop publishing.*" This highlights the importance of structural responses, including better metadata, search tools, and interdisciplinary collaboration.

4. Challenges and opportunities for crisis-responsive libraries

This section synthesizes the recurring findings from the survey and focus group discussions, highlighting the main challenges academic libraries face during crisis situations, alongside the opportunities that could strengthen their role in fostering individual and community resilience.

The visual below presents a conceptual overview of five thematic areas that emerged most prominently from the data:

1. The current role of libraries during crises,
2. Users' expectations and needs,
3. Structural and perceptual barriers,
4. Libraries' potential in public engagement and resilience, and
5. The growing concern around information overload.

Figure 5: Conceptual overview of key findings from the online survey and focus group data.

Source: Own construction.

Each of these themes encapsulates distinct tensions between what libraries offer, what users seek, and how those two dimensions connect—or fail to—in practice. Taken together, they form a diagnostic framework through which libraries' crisis-readiness can be critically examined and strategically strengthened.

4.1. Challenges identified

Despite being perceived as trusted, inclusive institutions, university libraries face several limitations that prevent them from fully responding to crisis contexts:

- **Low visibility and engagement:** While 81.8% of survey respondents believe libraries can play a meaningful role in crises, actual participation in community-oriented events remains limited. This reflects a gap between symbolic trust and practical engagement.
- **Lack of awareness of services:** Nearly half of respondents (44.2%) indicated that they were unaware of what libraries offer during crises, and over a third (37.2%) did not see libraries as particularly useful in such contexts.
- **Limited funding and resources:** Focus group participants stressed that libraries are often expected to do more with less, lacking the financial capacity or staffing to expand services or scale innovations during emergencies.

- **Insufficient crisis-specific competencies:** Many library staff members are not formally trained in mental health first aid, trauma-informed services, or digital information management skills that are increasingly necessary in complex crises.
- **Emotional disconnect or unwelcoming spaces:** Some respondents noted discomfort with library spaces or interactions, especially under stress, pointing to the need for more emotionally supportive and accessible environments.
- **Fragmented communication and outreach:** Both data sources confirmed that libraries struggle to promote their evolving roles and support services, particularly in digital spaces where competing sources often dominate attention.
- **Information overload:** 67.4% of respondents reported feeling overwhelmed by information, yet many lacked confidence in evaluating content. Libraries are not always perceived as primary guides through this complexity.

4.2. Opportunities ahead

While these challenges are significant, the data also reveal strong areas of potential for libraries to expand their crisis-responsiveness and social value:

- **High levels of trust:** Libraries are among the most trusted institutions. This positions them uniquely to offer calm, credible support during uncertain times, especially when other institutional trust may be lacking.
- **Existing infrastructure:** Libraries already offer valuable services such as digital access, curated content, remote assistance, and quiet, safe spaces. Building on these assets could enhance crisis utility with minimal restructuring.
- **Proven adaptability:** During the COVID-19 pandemic, libraries demonstrated agility by expanding digital offerings, supporting mental health through bibliotherapy, and creating safe physical environments. These experiences can be institutionalized and scaled.
- **Interest in educational interventions:** A majority of survey respondents (86.4%) expressed interest in library-led workshops to improve digital information literacy, highlighting a clear area for proactive programming.
- **Public engagement potential:** Libraries are well-positioned to serve as bridges between academic and civic spaces through hosting events, fostering dialogue, and supporting transdisciplinary, community-based initiatives.

- **Expanded roles in emotional and social support:** Open-ended responses and focus group insights revealed that users seek not just academic help, but empathetic staff, emotional safety, and a sense of belonging, especially in times of stress.
- **Becoming curators in the info-ecosystem:** Libraries can shift their identity from content providers to content navigators, guiding users through information overload with trustworthy, user-centered filtering and advisory services.

This dual lens of challenge and opportunity sets the stage for the final section of the report, where strategic recommendations will be outlined to help libraries realize their full potential in future crises.

5. Conclusion and recommendations

This report has explored the evolving role of university libraries in crisis contexts, drawing on survey responses and focus group discussions conducted by SKS Knowledge Services in May 2025. The findings confirm that while libraries are widely trusted and valued institutions, they face persistent challenges in fully realizing their potential as active crisis support actors.

Across multiple thematic areas such as crisis response, user expectations, barriers, engagement, and information overload. A clear pattern emerges: libraries are ready and willing, but not always recognized, resourced, or positioned to act. While users appreciate the emotional safety, digital resources, and neutral space that libraries provide, actual engagement remains low, and awareness of services during crises is limited.

The trust–usage gap is particularly telling: even among users who believe libraries can play a meaningful role, many do not turn to them in moments of need. This suggests that the issue is not only one of service delivery, but also of visibility, positioning, and perception.

In addition, the issue of information overload emerged as a crisis in its own right affecting decision-making, well-being, and academic performance. Libraries are well-placed to respond, but this will require reframing their roles as curators, educators, and digital navigators, not just content providers.

The focus group added important qualitative depth, highlighting both internal limitations (such as staff capacity and funding) and strategic opportunities (including collaborations, outreach, and public engagement). Participants emphasized the importance of libraries bridging gaps, not only between users and content, but between academic institutions and the broader communities they serve.

Based on the findings, the following recommendations are proposed to strengthen the capacity of academic libraries to support individuals and communities during crises:

1. Raise awareness of library crisis services

- Develop clear and proactive communication strategies before, during, and after crises.
- Promote available services more effectively across digital and physical platforms.
- Partner with student support offices and academic departments to increase reach.

2. Expand staff training and capacities

- Invest in training for library staff in areas such as trauma-informed communication, mental health first aid, and misinformation literacy.
- Encourage cross-training with student services, IT, and crisis response teams.

3. Strengthen infrastructure and resources

- Secure funding to enhance digital and remote access capabilities.
- Ensure availability of flexible spaces for mental health support, informal gatherings, or emergency shelter.

4. Position libraries as crisis communicators

- Develop library-led information hubs to deliver curated, real-time, multilingual content during emergencies.
- Embed libraries in institutional emergency planning teams and communication protocols.

5. Address information overload proactively

- Create workshops, tools, and personal guidance services to help users filter and assess complex or conflicting information.
- Leverage librarians' expertise in metadata, tagging, and relevance filtering.

6. Reinforce public engagement and community roles

- Host civic dialogues, exhibitions, and public events on crisis-related themes.
- Collaborate with local communities, NGOs, and civil society actors to co-create inclusive programming.

7. Reframe the library's identity

- Shift the narrative from library-as-building to library-as-platform as a dynamic, adaptive, and trusted actor in academic and civic life.
- Emphasize human presence and empathy as core elements of the library experience.

As crises grow more complex, blending social, political, environmental, and informational threats, university libraries must be empowered to act not only as quiet repositories, but as strategic, connected, and visible partners in resilience. This report highlights both the foundation already in place and the pathways forward.

Reference

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Annex I

Focus Group Discussion Questions

Background and role

Short introduction of participants and their role in the academic community.

I Experience with Crisis Contexts

What kinds of crises have you experienced or thought about?

How have these situations affected your research or personal life?

Where would you turn first for help in a crisis, and why?

II Library Roles During Crises

Do you consider libraries as trusted institutions in your community? Why or why not?

Have you ever received help or support from a library during a crisis?

How did the library respond (or could have responded) to the crisis during that time?

III Expectations and Needs

If such a crisis occurred tomorrow, what kind of support would be most important to you?

What would you expect from your library in this situation?

IV Barriers and Gaps

What are the main barriers that prevent libraries from supporting people in this specific crisis?

Are there reasons why you or others might not seek help from a library? If yes, how could we change it?

V Public Engagement & Community Resilience

Can you imagine a library being a place for community action or support? If yes, then how?

In your opinion, how can libraries build stronger communities during or after a crisis?

VI Case Specific Questions

Information overload is increasingly seen as a distinct crisis. Have you observed its effects at your institution, especially during recent crises?

How well do you think libraries are positioned to address information overload? What gaps or needs remain?

What practical support could libraries offer to help users manage information overload more effectively?

Annex II

Survey Questions

I Background information

1. Age *(select one option)*

18-25

26-35

36-45

46-60

61+

Prefer not to say

2. What is your current role within the academic community? *(Select the one you identify with the most)*

Student

Academic staff (e.g. lecturer, researcher)

Library staff

Administrative or support staff

Citizen scientist

I am not a member of the academic community

Other: _____

3. What type of crisis has affected you the most? *(Select one option)*

War or armed conflict

Political turbulence

Pandemic or health crisis

Mental health or well-being challenges in academic life

Information overload and challenges related to open science in research

Climate related crisis (e.g. heatwave, drought, flooding)

Disinformation during emergencies (e.g. war, disasters)

Problems with social integration or job opportunities for international students

Barriers faced by disabled people (e.g. access, inclusion)

Other: _____

3a. In your opinion, how much does each of the following scientific publication channels contribute to increased stress caused by information overload?

Please rate each on the following scale:

1 – No contribution

2 – Minimal contribution

3 – Moderate contribution

4 – Considerable contribution

5 – Heavy contribution

Scientific Publication Channel	1	2	3	4	5
Traditional peer-reviewed journals (in general)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Paywalled journals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Hybrid journals (subscription + Open Access option)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Fully Open Access (OA) journals	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Preprint servers (e.g., arXiv, bioRxiv, SSRN)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Institutional repositories (excluding preprints)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Subject-specific repositories (e.g., PubMed Central)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Conference proceedings and abstracts	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Edited volumes or book chapters	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Researcher profiles with uploads (e.g., ResearchGate)	<input type="checkbox"/>				
Data repositories with DOIs (e.g., Zenodo, Figshare)	<input type="checkbox"/>				

4. How do you usually find information during a crisis? (Select all that apply)

Social media

News media

Government websites

University websites or communication

Friends/family

Library channels

Academic journals or research sources

Other: _____

II Library Roles During Crises

5. Have you ever received support from a library during a crisis? Support could include practical help, information, or emotional support. *(Select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

5a. If yes, what kind of support did you receive?

Open question

6. In a crisis situation, which forms of support would you expect or seek from a library?
(Select all that apply)

Access to curated information

Internet or Wi-Fi

Charging stations

Physical space for study/work

Mental health support or safe environment

Cultural events and social interaction

Help with government forms or aid

Emergency supplies (masks, flashlights, etc.)

Online library services (ebooks, databases, etc.)

Guidance for using academic databases

Training sessions and courses

Support for research or community projects that respond to the crisis

I wouldn't expect anything from a library

Other: _____

III Expectations and Needs

7. When facing a crisis, how important would each of the following be for you personally? Some of these needs may be supported by libraries, others may not. Please rate how important each would be to you personally in a crisis. (Rate each from "Not at all important" to "Very important")

	Not at all important	Slightly important	Moderately important	Important	Very important
Access to credible, accurate, and curated information					
Reliable internet access					
Access to physical space or shelter					
Community connection					
Support for mental health					
Online library access					
Emergency information updates					
Assistance with digital tools					
Being part of the solution					
Opportunities for collaboration or problem-solving with others					
Feeling informed and involved					

8. What would make a library feel like a supportive and safe space during a crisis (e.g., space, staff, resources)?

Open question

IV Barriers and Support Gaps

9. What might prevent you from using library services in a crisis? (Select all that apply)

Library is closed

Difficult to find up-to-date information from the library website and social media channels

Library location is hard to reach

Library is not accessible or inclusive for disabled users

Library has no internet access

Didn't know library could help

Negative past experiences at the library

Lack of trust in libraries

Other: _____

10. Would you feel comfortable approaching a library for help in crisis? *(select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

10a. If you answered "No" or "Not sure," please explain why:

Open question

V Public Engagement and Community Support

11. Do you agree with the following statement: Libraries can play a meaningful role in supporting communities during crises.

Strongly disagree

Disagree

Neither agree nor disagree

Agree

Strongly agree

12. Have you ever participated in any community-focused events or activities at your university library? *(Select one option)*

Yes

No

Not sure

12a. If yes, what kind of activity or event was it?

Open question

13. What activities or services could a library offer to support your community in difficult times?

Open question

VI Optional Section – Information Overload

14. Have you experienced information overload related to your academic or professional activities?

Yes

No

Not sure

15. What were the main sources that contributed to this information overload?

(Select all that apply)

Social media platforms (e.g. Facebook, LinkedIn, X)

Academic publications and research databases

News websites or continuous media coverage

Messaging apps (e.g. Telegram, WhatsApp)

University or institutional communications

Library services or newsletters

Government communications

Friends, family, or community discussions

Other: _____

16. What challenges did you face due to information overload?

(Select all that apply)

Difficulty identifying relevant or high-quality content

Confusion due to conflicting information

Feeling overwhelmed by volume of information

Decreased productivity or focus

Difficulty in making decisions

Other: _____

17. How did you try to manage or cope with the information overload?

(Select all that apply)

Limited the time spent engaging with information

Focused on a few trusted sources

Consulted peers, librarians, or staff for guidance

Used curated resources provided by the library

Participated in webinars or workshops to enhance information literacy

Did not take specific actions

Other: _____

18. How confident are you in your ability to evaluate the credibility of information?

Not at all confident

Slightly confident

Moderately confident

Confident

Very confident

19. Would you find it useful if your library offered resources or workshops on spotting disinformation and evaluating information credibility?

Yes

Maybe

No

20. In your view, what is the most important thing libraries should do to help people cope with too much information?

Open question

21. Do you have anything to add?

Open question